

Synthesis of some newer thiazolidinones

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Abstract : Some new 2-[2'-substituted-4'-thiazolidinon-3'-yl]-5,6-dimethyl-8,9-dihydro-10H-benzo[7]annuleno[9,8-d]thiazoles (5a-f) have been synthesized by 1,3-cyclocondensation of thioglycolic acid with 1-substituted-N-(5,6-dimethyl-8,9-dihydro-10H-benzo[7]annuleno[9,8-d]thiazol-2-yl)methanimines (4a-f). The structures of all these compounds have been delineated by elemental analysis and spectral studies (IR, ¹H NMR and Mass).

Keywords : Benzosuberones, thiazolidinone.

Introduction

In view of the potential biological activity of 4-thiazolidinones¹⁻⁸ and in continuation of our interest in the synthesis of biologically active fused heterocycles⁹⁻¹¹, it was thought worthwhile to prepare the title compounds with the hope that these new ring systems prove to be biologically active. The title compounds were prepared according to Scheme 1. Reaction of benzosuberone **1** with hydrogen bromide and hydrogen peroxide gave 6-bromo-2,3-dimethyl-6,7,8,9-tetrahydrobenzo[7]annulen-5-one (**2**). The compound **2** on cyclocondensation with thiourea gave

5,6-dimethyl-10H-benzo[7]annuleno[9,8-d]thiazol-2-amine (**3**) in 84% yield. The IR spectrum of **3** showed characteristic band at 3280 cm⁻¹ (NH₂) and also the disappearance of the C=O absorption band of **2**. Compound **3**, when treated with various aromatic aldehydes in absolute ethanol and a few drops of glacial acetic acid, resulted the corresponding derivatives **4a-f**. Absorption band at 1600–1620 cm⁻¹ (C=N) in the IR spectra, and a sharp singlet at δ 9.10 (1H, s, N=CH-Ar) in ¹H NMR spectrum clearly indicate the formation of the compounds **4a-f**. Compounds **4a-f** on cyclocondensation with thioglycolic acid in the presence of anhydrous zinc chlo-

Scheme 1

Table 1. Physical, analytical and spectral data of compounds 5a-f

Compd.	M.p. (°C)	Yield (%)	Mol. formula (mol. wt)	Found (Calcd.) (%)			IR (KBr) (cm ⁻¹)	¹ H NMR (δ ppm)
				C	H	N		
5a	70-72	52	C ₂₄ H ₂₄ N ₂ S ₂ O ₂ (436)	66.03 (66.08)	5.48 (5.52)	6.40 (6.44)	1610 (C=N), 1691 (C=O), 1143 (C-S)	1.95-2.00 (2H, m, 10-CH ₂), 2.20 (6H, s, 5- and 6-CH ₃), 2.65-2.70 (2H, m, 9-CH ₂), 2.82-3.00 (2H, m, 8-CH ₂), 3.78 (3H, s, -OCH ₃), 3.82-3.90 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 16.60 Hz, S-CH ₂), 4.10-4.91 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 16.60 Hz, S-CH ₂), 6.65 (1H, s, S-CH), 6.81-7.42 (6H, m, Ar-H)
5b	90-93	40	C ₂₃ H ₂₂ N ₂ S ₂ O (406)	67.98 (68.00)	5.41 (5.44)	6.89 (6.91)	1600 (C=N), 1696 (C=O), 1140 (C-S)	1.85-1.95 (2H, m, 10-CH ₂), 2.20 (6H, s, 5- and 6-CH ₃), 2.62-2.78 (2H, m, 9-CH ₂), 2.82-3.10 (2H, m, 8-CH ₂), 3.81-3.95 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 16.60 Hz, S-CH ₂), 4.15-4.20 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 16.60 Hz, S-CH ₂), 6.65 (1H, s, S-CH), 7.20-7.50 (7H, m, Ar-H)
5c	168-170	56	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₂ S ₂ O ₂ (396)	63.62 (63.65)	5.04 (5.07)	7.06 (7.80)	1522 (C=N), 1689 (C=O), 1142 (C-S)	2.00-2.10 (2H, m, 10-CH ₂), 2.25 (6H, s, 5- and 6-CH ₃), 2.70-2.80 (2H, m, 9-CH ₂), 2.90-3.01 (2H, m, 8-CH ₂), 3.65-3.81 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 16.60 Hz, S-CH ₂), 4.19-4.25 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 16.60 Hz, S-CH ₂), 6.30 (1H, s, S-CH), 6.40-7.65 (5H, m, Ar-H)
5d	150-153	53	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₂ S ₃ O (412)	61.16 (61.18)	4.85 (4.87)	6.79 (6.81)	1654 (C=N), 1696 (C=O), 1145 (C-S)	2.00-2.20 (2H, m, 10-CH ₂), 2.25 (6H, s, 5- and 6-CH ₃), 2.70-2.80 (2H, m, 9-CH ₂), 2.95-3.15 (2H, m, 8-CH ₂), 3.75-3.85 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 16.60 Hz, S-CH ₂), 4.15-4.25 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 16.60 Hz, S-CH ₂), 6.50 (1H, s, S-CH), 6.90-7.70 (6H, m, Ar-H)
5e	148-150	45	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ N ₃ S ₂ O (407)	64.84 (64.89)	5.13 (5.17)	10.30 (10.33)	1617 (C=N), 1686 (C=O), 1140 (C-S)	1.90-2.20 (2H, m, 10-CH ₂), 2.30 (6H, s, 5- and 6-CH ₃), 2.65-2.80 (2H, m, 9-CH ₂), 2.85-3.15 (2H, m, 8-CH ₂), 3.70-3.80 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 16.60 Hz, S-CH ₂), 4.25-4.40 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 16.60 Hz, S-CH ₂), 6.60 (1H, s, S-CH), 6.80-7.80 (5H, m, Ar-H), 8.60 (1H, d, N=CH)
5f	120-122	42	C ₂₄ H ₂₄ N ₂ S ₂ O (420)	68.55 (68.59)	5.70 (5.73)	6.64 (6.68)	1600 (C=N), 1695 (C=O), 1142 (C-S)	1.85-2.05 (2H, m, 10-CH ₂), 2.20 (6H, s, 5- and 6-CH ₃), 2.35 (3H, s, Ph-CH ₃), 2.68-2.80 (2H, m, 9-CH ₂), 2.89-3.05 (2H, m, 8-CH ₂), 3.80-3.90 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 16.60 Hz, S-CH ₂), 4.08-4.18 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 16.60 Hz, S-CH ₂), 6.65 (1H, s, S-CH), 6.80-7.40 (6H, m, Ar-H)

ride resulting in the formation of thiazolidinone ring systems 5a-f. IR spectrum of 5a-f exhibited sharp absorption bands due to C=O (1690 cm⁻¹) and C-S (1140 cm⁻¹), which indicates the presence of β-thiolactam ring. Further,

appearance of signals at δ 6.65 (1H, s, S-CH-Ar), 3.80 (1H, d, *J* 16.60 Hz, S-CH₂) and 4.20 (1H, d, *J* 16.60 Hz, S-CH₂) in the ¹H NMR spectrum confirms the presence of thiazolidinone ring.

Biological evaluation :**Antimicrobial activity :**

All the compounds were screened for their antimicrobial activity at a concentration of 10 µg/well in agar media¹² using Rifampicin in antibacterial and Clotrimazole in antifungal activities as reference compounds. Compounds **2**, **3**, **5a**, **5b**, **5e** showed maximum activity in terms of diameter of the zone of inhibition (8–10 mm) as compared with Rifampicin (13 mm) against gram +ve bacterium *Staphylococcus*, while all the other compounds were found resistant towards gram -ve bacterium *E. coli*. All compounds are ineffective against the fungus *Trichoderma* species.

Analgesic and anti-inflammatory activities :

Analgesic and anti-inflammatory activities of the compounds were determined by Turner¹³ writhing test and rat-paw edema test¹⁴. The inhibition of the edema was recorded on a plethysmometer (UGO BASILE make) and expressed as % inhibition. Compounds **2**, **3**, **5a**, **5b**, **5e** exhibited greater degree showed (30–32%) of edema in rats on comparison with aspirin and phenylbutazone at the same dose (100 mg/kg), produced 17% and 39% inhibition of 1% carrageenan induced inflammation, respectively.

Compounds exhibited significant anti-inflammatory activity better than aspirin but comparable with that of phenylbutazone. However, they were found to possess less analgesic with reference to aspirin.

Experimental

Melting points were determined using Gallankamp apparatus and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on a FT-IR 1605 Perkin-Elmer, ¹H NMR in CDCl₃ on a Varian 200 MHz spectrometer with TMS as internal standard and mass spectra on a VG-micromass 7070H mass spectrometer. TLC was run on silica gel-G coated plates and iodine vapor as visualizing agent.

6-Bromo-2,3-dimethyl-6,7,8,9-tetrahydrobenzo[7]annulen-5-one (2) : To a well stirred solution of hydrogen peroxide (70% aq. 0.058 g, 0.0017 mol) and hydrobromic acid (48% aq. 0.13 g, 0.0017 mol) in methanol, benzosuberone (**1**) (0.3 g, 0.0017 mol) in methanol was added drop by drop at 0–5 °C during 10 min. The reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 30 min and then refluxed for 24 h. The solution was concen-

trated to dryness *in vacuo* and the residue was dissolved in water extracted with chloroform. The organic layer was worked up in the usual way to give gummy compound, which was purified by column chromatography using silica gel with ethyl acetate-petroleum ether as eluant (1 : 9) to give semi-solid **2**, yield 55% (Found : C, 58.20; H, 5.59. Calcd. for C₁₃H₁₅OBr : C, 58.25; H, 5.60%); IR (KBr) : 1730 cm⁻¹(C=O); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 1.90–2.05 (2H, m, 7-CH₂), 2.30 (6H, s, 2- and 3-CH₃), 2.80–3.10 (4H, m, 8- and 9-CH₂), 4.85 (1H, t, Br-CH), 6.80 (1H, s, Ar-H), 7.50 (1H, s, Ar-H).

5,6-Dimethyl-10H-benzo[7]annuleno[9,8-d]thiazol-2-amine (3) : A mixture of compound **2** (0.00015 mol) and thiourea (0.00015 mol) in water (5 ml) was heated under reflux for 1 h. After completion of the reaction as monitored by TLC, it was neutralized with 5% of ammonia and extracted with chloroform (20 mL). The organic layer was worked up in the usual way and the crude product was purified by column chromatography over silica gel with ethyl acetate-petroleum ether as eluant (1 : 9) to afford **3**, yield 84%; m.p. 140–141 °C (Found : C, 68.85; H, 6.55; N, 11.47. Calcd. for C₁₄H₁₆N₂S : C, 68.89; H, 6.58; N, 11.49%); IR (KBr) : 3280 cm⁻¹(NH₂); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 2.00–2.18 (2H, m, 10-CH₂), 2.24 (6H, s, 5- and 6-CH₃), 2.70–2.90 (4H, m, 8-CH₂ + 9-CH₂), 4.80–5.10 (2H, bs, -NH₂), 6.85 (1H, s, Ar-H), 7.65 (1H, s, Ar-H); MS : *m/z* 244 (M⁺).

1-Substituted-N-(5,6-dimethyl-8,9-dihydro-10H-benzo[7]annuleno[9,8-d]thiazol-2-yl)methanimines (4a-f) : **General procedure :** A mixture of 5,6-dimethyl-10H-benzo[7]annuleno[9,8-d]thiazol-2-amine (**3**) (0.0002 mol), 4-methoxy benzaldehyde (0.0002 mol) in ethanol and few drops of glacial acetic acid was refluxed for 10–12 h. After completion of the reaction, as monitored by TLC, the excess solvent was distilled off and the concentrate was poured into ice-water. It was then extracted with chloroform, concentrated *in vacuo* and chromatographed over silica gel with ethyl acetate-petroleum ether as eluant (1 : 9) afforded **4a**. Yield 58%; m.p. 120–122 °C (Found : C, 72.92; H, 6.07; N, 7.73. Calcd. for C₂₂H₂₂N₂SO : C, 72.95; H, 6.10; N, 7.75%); IR (KBr) : 1600–1620 (C=N), 1500 cm⁻¹(C=C); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 2.22–2.35 (2H, m, 10-CH₂), 2.38 (6H, s, 5- and 6-CH₃), 2.60–2.72 (2H, m, 9-CH₂), 2.72–2.90 (2H, m, 8-CH₂), 3.82 (3H, s, -OCH₃), 6.80–8.10 (6H, m, Ar-H), 9.15 (1H, s, N=CH).

4b. Yield 55%; m.p. 151–152 °C (Found : C, 75.90; H, 6.02; N, 8.42. Calcd. for $C_{21}H_{20}N_2S$: C, 75.93; H, 6.05; N, 8.45%).

4c. Yield 60%; m.p. 178–180 °C (Found : C, 70.80; H, 5.59; N, 8.69. Calcd. for $C_{19}H_{18}N_2O$: C, 70.83; H, 5.61; N, 8.70%).

4d. Yield 58%; m.p. 161–163 °C (Found : C, 67.45; H, 5.32; N, 8.28. Calcd. for $C_{19}H_{18}N_2S_2$: C, 67.48; H, 5.35; N, 8.30%).

4e. Yield 57%; m.p. 169–171 °C (Found : C, 72.07; H, 5.70; N, 12.61. Calcd. for $C_{20}H_{19}N_3S$: C, 72.10; H, 5.72; N, 12.63%).

4f. Yield 49%; m.p. 152–154 °C (Found : C, 76.30; H, 6.35; N, 8.09. Calcd. for $C_{22}H_{22}N_2S$: C, 76.35; H, 6.38; N, 8.11%).

2-[2'-Substituted-4'-thiazolidinon-3'-yl]-5,6-dimethyl-8,9-dihydro-10H-benzo[7]annuleno[9,8-d]thiazoles (5a-f) :
General procedure : A pinch of anhydrous $ZnCl_2$ and thioglycolic acid (0.0011 mol) was added to a stirred solution of **4a-f** (0.00055 mol) in absolute ethanol and was refluxed for 1 h. The excess solvent was removed *in vacuo* and diluted with water. The reaction mixture was then extracted with chloroform and evaporated to give a crude residue which was purified by column chromatography over silica gel with ethyl acetate-petroleum ether (1 : 9) as eluant to afford **5a-f**.

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